

Caregiver Burden, Parental Stress, Depression and Anxiety among Mothers of Autism Spectrum Disorder

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ABSTRACT

Background: The growing incidence of autism spectrum disorder (ASD) in India raises the urgency for nation-wide awareness and accessible intervention programs. Mothers who are the primary caregivers face challenges while balancing the maternal, societal and professional responsibilities. Addressing their mental health needs is vital, as chronic stress can lead to depression and burnout, affecting their overall well-being and also ability to care for their child. **Aim:** The present study seeks to endeavour the difference in experiencing caregiver burden, parental stress, depression and anxiety among mothers of children having ASD and typically developing children. **Method:** Between group design was used on a sample of 200 mothers (100mothers of typically developing children and 100 mothers of children having ASD with mild to moderate disability) selected using purposive sampling technique who voluntarily participated in the study. **Materials:** Burden Assessment Schedule and Depression Anxiety and Stress in Parents of Children with Special Needs were used to measure caregiver burden, stress, anxiety and depression in the mother's of both the groups. **Result:** ASD mothers reported significantly higher level of burden than mothers of typically developing children. Mothers of ASD child perceived higher level of stress, anxiety and depression as compared to mothers of typically developing children.

Keywords: *Autism Spectrum Disorder, Caregiver burden, Parental stress, Depression, Anxiety*

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Introduction

One of the neuro-developmental conditions that emerges in early childhood and affects individuals into the adulthood is autism spectrum disorder (ASD). It is distinguished by irregular patterns of delay and differences in the development of social, communicative and cognitive skills. Children suffering from autism spectrum disorder show some symptoms within few years of their life. Social impairments include challenges in nonverbal behaviors while interaction, development of inappropriate peer relations and poor social or emotional interactions. Symptoms encompasses lack of eye contact with people, present with lack of social smile, not able to express emotion, some repetitive or restricted pattern of behaviour and actions and many more. It ranges from mild to severe form and hence termed as "spectrum" disorder.

The prevalence rate of ASD seems to be rising all over the world, including India. As stated in the World Health Organization's 2019 fact sheet the proportion of children diagnosed with ASD is approximately 1 in 100 worldwide. According to the report of NCBI the overall prevalence rate of ASD in India among rural, urban and tribal children was about 0.9% or 1 among 115 children¹. The rises in cases of ASD come with challenge for the mothers who are generally the primary care-givers of the autistic children and poses significant burden on physical and mental health of families, caregivers and mothers.

Caregiver burden can be understood as the burden which person experience in the process of giving care to the individual with any severe or chronic health condition or person with disability. Caregiver burden has been defined as the stress or load a person bears while offering care for a family member with chronically illness, disability or age related challenges (Stucki & Mulvey, 2000)². In traditional societies, mostly in Indian households, mothers are usually the primary caregivers and they face most significant burden. The burden of care giving to child with ASD deals with providing the needs and balancing other responsibilities such as management of household, care of other household members, managing job (if employed), all these factors can lead to mental, physical, financial and emotional strain on mother.

The child with ASD needs special parenting which can be stressful and a challenging experience. Various studies have shown the parents with ASD child suffer with stress more than in comparison to the children who are non-autistic.³ **Parenting stress** is described as a series of events that typically result into unpleasant psychological and physical reactions as one tries to adjust to the demands of the parenting position. Tantrums, aggression and self harm are the challenging behaviour of the child in social setting which care-giver of the children with ASD faces, specially the mother. These challenges lead to more distress in mother. The child's behaviour could be misunderstood by the family and society which is associated with social isolation of mothers and for a prolonged period leads to anxiety and depression.

Anxiety and depression generally goes hand-in-hand. Anxiety can be described as the feeling of excessive worry and fear and it can be one of the symptoms of depression. Depression can be understood as feeling of sadness and hopelessness. The child's inability to perform daily activities and mother being present all the time with child and giving extra care to monitor their child's behaviour and safety makes parenting challenging for a child with ASD. These challenges faced by mother on daily basis increases the chances of mother being vulnerable to anxiety and depression due to overwhelming nature of care giving.

Caregiver Burden, Stress, Anxiety and Depression

The level of caregiver burden is more in the in the parents of children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) as compared to the parents of typically developing children⁴. Since, the parents need to manage the emotional and behavioral difficulties of the child⁵, they experience greater level of stress. The level of stress, anxiety and depression has been found to be more in the mothers as compared to fathers of children with ASD⁶. Altieri and Von Kluge (2009)⁷ reported that taking care of children with ASD significantly affects the physical, financial and mental health of the caregivers. Later, Merkaj et al., (2013)⁸ reported increased level of parental stress, depression and anxiety among parents of children having ASD in comparison to parents of typically developing children. Recently, Hoopen et al. (2020)⁹ reported significant relation between caregiver burden and parental stress among the primary and secondary caregivers of children with ASD.

However, mother's experiences more parenting stress as compare to fathers. Benson (2008)⁴ reported that among the parents, mothers are the one who generally experiences more stress as they have to maintain balance between the care-giving duties and household work. Other studies (e.g., Salem Guirgis et al, 2019)¹⁰ also reported that mothers of ASD children experiences higher level of parenting stress as they link themselves with social stigma due to developmental differences of their child with the healthy child.

Higher level of stress heightens the risk of psychiatric disorders including anxiety and depression among the caregivers of children with ASD¹¹. These parents experienced difficulties in psychological and personal well-being and coping from the care giving stress. Regulating their child's atypical behavior creates maternal stress and also high rates of depression among mothers having ASD child¹². Studies Swinkels, (2019)¹³ have reported that mother's shows higher level of psychological distress and depression as compared to fathers of the ASD child.

Countries with scarcity of resources and support systems, providing care to children with ASD is more stressful and challenging. Weitlauf et al., (2014)¹⁴ in their study reported that parents with ASD child had higher levels of anxiety and depression as compared to parents of normally developing children. Parenting stress is also high in parents with ASD child as compared to parents of other neuro-developmental disabilities¹⁵. This is due to the challenging symptoms of the disorder which requires extensive care to manage and leads to greater amount of stress, anxiety and depression ¹⁶.

Rationale

Offering care to children can be satisfying but it is demanding and challenging too. Primary caregivers who are the mothers of children often go through a lot of physical and psychological strain. Researches have been done for comparing the parenting stress among the parents as well as among the parents of disabled child and normal developed child. But, there has been paucity in studies in explaining burden of care giving among the mothers of children having ASD and typically developing children. The present study seeks to endeavour the difference in experiencing caregiver burden, parental stress, depression and anxiety among mothers of children having ASD and typically developing children.

Hypothesis

- There will be a significant difference in caregiver burden among mothers of children with ASD and mothers of typically developing children.
- There will be significant difference in anxiety, depression and stress among mothers of children with ASD and mothers of typically developing children.

Method

Sample- A total of 200 mothers were selected for the sample who voluntarily participated in the study. Among them, 100 were the mothers of typically developing children (mean age of 32.95 years) and 100 were the mothers of children having ASD (mean age of 35.03 years). Mothers whose child had mild to moderate disability of Autism Spectrum Disorder were included. Mothers of child having other disabilities and suffering from any major physical or psychological condition were excluded. Purposive sampling was used. The data was collected from mental health institutions, NGOs and schools in New Delhi.

Tools

Burden Assessment Schedule: Hindi adaptation (Khusboo & Bajpai, 2023)¹⁷ for the caregivers of children with developmental disabilities. Burden Assessment Schedule was originally developed in English language, at SCARF (Schizophrenia Research Foundation, India). The schedule consists of 40 items scored on 3-point scale of “not at all”, “to some extent” and “very much”. Reliability coefficient of Objective burden is 0.73 whereas for subjective burden is 0.86. Criterion validity of this scale is 0.71- 0.82.

Depression Anxiety and Stress in parents of children with special needs: The scale was developed by Narain and Singh (2021)¹⁸. This scale has 35 items which measures three dimensions depression (15), anxiety (08) and stress (12). The response alternatives are on 5-point response scale from “strongly disagree”, “disagree”, “neutral”, “agree”, and “strongly agree”. Reliability of the scale is 0.91 and validity of the scale is 0.73.

Procedure

Mothers of typically developing children were selected by contacting them in schools and taking permission from the principal. During parent teacher meet purpose of the research was acknowledged to the parents. After establishing rapport, consent was taken and questionnaires were filled with appropriate instructions.

For collecting data from mothers of children having ASD, mental health institutions and NGOs were contacted. Mothers coming for the session of their children were selected. Purpose of the research was debriefed. After establishing rapport with each mothers consent was taken and questionnaires were filled with appropriate instructions. After questionnaires being filled, participants were thanked for their valuable support and time. Further the scoring was done and data was analyzed using suitable statistics.

Result

Caregiver Burden of mothers was analyzed using Burden Assessment Schedule. Higher level of caregiver burden (77.8 ± 8.6) was reported by the mothers of children having ASD than mothers of typically developing children (67.2 ± 11.8). The result is graphically shown in Figure-1. The difference between both the groups showed a significant difference $t(198) = 7.29$, $p = 0.00$. This suggests that having ASD child, mothers experience more burden in giving care to their child as compared to mothers of TDC.

Figure 1: Mean score of mothers of both groups on Caregiver Burden

On the anxiety component, mothers of children having ASD scored higher (31.2 ± 6.9) than mothers of typically developing children (28.4 ± 8.6). The mean scores represent mothers of children having ASD as highly anxious as compared to mothers of typically developing children who are moderately anxious. The difference between the means of mothers is $t(198) = 2.5$, $p = 0.012$ which reveals a significant difference on the anxiety dimension of the scale. On the depression component mean of mothers of children with ASD was higher (48.3 ± 12.7) than mean of mothers of normal children (38.4 ± 15.2).

The mean scores of the mothers represents moderate depression among the mothers of children with ASD whereas low depression among mothers of typically developing children. The difference between both the groups is a significant, $t(198) = 5.02$, $p = 0.00$.

On the stress component mean of mothers with ASD is higher (37.8 ± 8.9) than mean of mothers of typically developing children (35.1 ± 10.6). The mean scores of the mothers of both the group represent moderate stress. The difference between both the means is $t(198) = 1.98$, $p = 0.05$ which reveals a significant difference between both the groups though the differences between both the mean scores is 2.7. The mean \pm SD of both the groups on anxiety, depression and stress scales is graphically presented in Figure 2.

Figure-2: Mean score of mothers of both groups on Anxiety, Depression and Stress

Discussion

The present study seeks to explore the role of caregiver burden, anxiety, depression and stress among mothers of children having Autism spectrum disorder and mothers of typically developing children. The results revealed that mothers of children having ASD and mothers of typically developing children differ significantly on caregiver burden. Mothers of children having ASD scored higher level of burden than the mothers of typically developing children. Thus the first hypothesis i.e., *There will be significant difference in caregiver burden among mothers of children with ASD and mothers of typically developing children* is accepted. The present finding gets supported from Hoopen et al., (2020)⁹ who also reported significant association between caregiver burden and parental stress in those families where the child is diagnosed with ASD. Altieri J and Von Kluge (2009)⁷ also revealed that taking care of the child with ASD has placed burden on the physical, financial, and mental health of the caregivers. In conclusion, these studies underscores the fact that primary caregivers who are the mothers of the children experiences burden in terms of caring their ASD child.

Further the results revealed that mothers of children having ASD and mothers of typically developing children differ significantly on scores of anxiety, depression and stress subscales. Mothers of children having ASD were highly anxious whereas mothers of typically developing children were moderately anxious. Also, the results indicated that mothers of children having ASD were moderately depressed whereas mothers of typically developing children were less depressed. The difference between mean scores of mothers of both the groups on stress subscale was very less (2.97), yet both the groups differed significantly. According to the norm table the scores on the subscale indicate that mothers of children having ASD as well as mothers of typically developing children had moderate stress. Thus, the second hypothesis i.e., *there will be significant difference in anxiety, depression and stress among mothers of children with ASD and mothers of typically developing children* is accepted. The present findings also get supported from findings of Weitlauf, et al., (2014)¹⁴ reported that level of anxiety and depression was more in parents of children having ASD when compared to the parents of normally developing children. Findings of Kotera, et. al, (2019)¹⁵ indicated greater amount of parenting stress among ASD parents due to the challenging symptoms of the disorder which requires extensive care to manage in comparison to the parents of children with other neuro-developmental disabilities. The findings of Ingersoll & Hambrick (2011)¹² explained that regulating the child's atypical behaviour creates maternal stress and also heightened proportion of depression among mothers of children having ASD. In conclusion these findings highlights the challenging and demanding care giving for the ASD child which affects the well being and mental health of their mothers leading to heightened levels of stress, anxiety and depression.

Conclusion

Parents and families having ASD child have to go through a network of negative experiences. Raising a child with ASD takes a lot from the families as they have to create a balance between all the commitments by withdrawing themselves from all the social interactions. Secondly, they have to deal with all the stigma and discriminatory behaviours from their community. These parents actively have to deal with all the social challenges by using appropriate coping strategies and exploring all the beneficial support from their friends, family, and mental health care professionals. Thus, the support services being provided to such mothers will help them to develop effective strategies to manage the challenging tasks of giving care to their child with autism spectrum disorder.

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